

A Study of the Influence of College Students' Exercise and Leisure Motivations on the Leisure Benefits: Using Leisure Involvement as a Moderator

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Abstract : This study aim at the influence of college students' exercise and leisure motivations on the leisure benefits while using the leisure involvement as a moderator. Whereby, the research tools used in this study included the application of leisure motivation scale, leisure involvement scale and leisure benefits scale, and a hierarchical regression analysis was performed by using a questionnaire-based survey, in which, a total of 1,500 copies of questionnaires were administered and 917 valid questionnaires were obtained, achieving a response rate of 61.13%. Research findings explore that leisure involvement has a moderating effect on the relationship between the leisure motivation and leisure benefits.

Keywords : leisure motivation, leisure involvement, leisure benefits, moderator

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